

ON A VARIATION OF THE COIN EXCHANGE PROBLEM FOR ARITHMETIC PROGRESSIONS

Amitabha Tripathi

Department of Mathematics, Indian Institute of Technology, Hauz Khas, New Delhi - 110016, India
atripath@maths.iitd.ac.in

Received: 3/21/02, Revised: 10/24/02, Accepted: 1/1/03, Published: 1/2/03

Abstract

Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k be relatively prime, positive integers arranged in increasing order. Let Γ^* denote the positive integers in the set $\{a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_kx_k : x_j \geq 0\}$. Let

$$\mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \doteq \{n \notin \Gamma^* : n + \Gamma^* \subseteq \Gamma^*\}.$$

We determine $\mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ in the case where the a_j 's are in *arithmetic progression*. In particular, this determines $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ in this particular case.

1. Introduction

Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k be relatively prime, positive integers arranged in increasing order. Let Γ denote $\{a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_kx_k : x_j \geq 0\}$, and let $\Gamma^* \doteq \Gamma \setminus \{0\}$. It is well known and easy to show that $\Gamma^c \doteq \mathbb{N} \setminus \Gamma$ is a *finite* set. We use the classical notation $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ to denote the *largest* number in Γ^c . *J.J. Sylvester* [15] showed that $g(a_1, a_2) = a_1a_2 - a_1 - a_2$. In later years, the number of elements in Γ^c , denoted by $n(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$, was also studied, and it was shown that $n(a_1, a_2) = (a_1 - 1)(a_2 - 1)/2$. Another function related to this is the function $s(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ that denotes the sum of elements in Γ^c . Introduced in [4], it was shown that $s(a_1, a_2) = (a_1 - 1)(a_2 - 1)(2a_1a_2 - a_1 - a_2 - 1)/12$.

There is a neat formula for each of the functions g and n when the a_j 's are in *arithmetic progression* ([1],[5],[9],[16]), but other results obtained are mostly partial results ([2],[3],[6],[7],[10],[11], [12],[13],[14]) and often not as neat. Due to an obvious connection with making change given money of different denominations, this problem is also known as the *Coin Exchange Problem*.

2. Main Result

We study a variation of the Coin Exchange Problem in this note. We denote by $\mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ the set of all $n \in \Gamma^c$ such that

$$n + \Gamma^* \subseteq \Gamma^*,$$

and let $g^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ (respectively, $n^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ and $s^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$) denote the *least* (respectively, the *number* and *sum* of) elements in \mathcal{S}^* . Since $g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is the *largest* element in \mathcal{S}^* ,

$$g^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \leq g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k),$$

and $n^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \geq 1$, with equality if and only if $g^* = g$. This problem arises from looking at the generators for the Derivation modules of certain curves [8], and has been extensively studied.

For each j , $1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1$, let m_j denote the *least* number in Γ congruent to $j \pmod{a_1}$. Then $m_j - a_1$ is the largest number in Γ^c congruent to $j \pmod{a_1}$, and no number less than this in this residue class can be in \mathcal{S}^* , for they would differ by a multiple of a_1 , an element in Γ^* . Therefore,

$$\mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \subseteq \{m_j - a_1 : 1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1\}, \tag{1}$$

$$g^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \leq \left(\max_{1 \leq j \leq a_1 - 1} m_j\right) - a_1 = g(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k), \tag{2}$$

$$n^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \leq a_1 - 1, \tag{3}$$

and

$$s^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \leq \sum_{j=1}^{a_1-1} m_j - a_1(a_1 - 1). \tag{4}$$

More precisely,

$$m_j - a_1 \in \mathcal{S}^*(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \iff (m_j - a_1) + m_i \geq m_{j+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq a_1 - 1. \tag{5}$$

We shall explicitly evaluate the set \mathcal{S}^* , and as a consequence, the functions g , g^* , n^* and s^* , when the a_j 's are in *arithmetic progression*. We write $a_j = a + (j - 1)d$ for $1 \leq j \leq k$, and assume $\gcd(a, d) = 1$. In this case, we denote the functions g , g^* , n^* and s^* by $g(a, d; k)$, $g^*(a, d; k)$, $n^*(a, d; k)$ and $s^*(a, d; k)$, respectively. To determine $\mathcal{S}^*(a, d; k)$, we recall Lemma 2 from [16].

Lemma: For each t , $1 \leq t \leq a - 1$, the least integer in Γ^* congruent to $dt \pmod{a}$

is given by $a(1 + \lfloor \frac{t-1}{k-1} \rfloor) + dt$.

Theorem: Let a, d be relatively prime, positive integers, and let $k \geq 2$. If $a - 1 = q(k - 1) + r$, with $1 \leq r \leq k - 1$, then

$$\mathcal{S}^*(a, d; k) = \left\{ a \left\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + dx : a - r \leq x \leq a - 1 \right\}.$$

PROOF: Fix $k \geq 2$. Throughout this proof, and elsewhere, by $x \bmod m$ we mean $x - x \lfloor \frac{x}{m} \rfloor$. By (1) and Lemma,

$$\mathcal{S}^*(a, d; k) \subseteq \left\{ a \left\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + dx : 1 \leq x \leq a - 1 \right\}.$$

From (5), $n = a \lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \rfloor + dx \in \mathcal{S}^*$ if and only if for each y with $1 \leq y \leq a - 1$,

$$a \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{((x+y) \bmod a) - 1}{k-1} \right\rfloor \right) + d((x+y) \bmod a) \leq \left\{ a \left\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + dx \right\} + \left\{ a \left(1 + \left\lfloor \frac{y-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor \right) + dy \right\},$$

or,

$$a \left\lfloor \frac{((x+y) \bmod a) - 1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + d((x+y) \bmod a) \leq a \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{y-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor \right\} + d(x+y). \quad (6)$$

Suppose $2 \leq k \leq a - 1$. Let $a - 1 = q(k - 1) + r$, with $1 \leq r \leq k - 1$. Unless $x = a - 1$, $x + y \leq a - 1$ for at least one y , for such a y , (6) reduces to proving the inequality

$$\left\lfloor \frac{x+y-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor \leq \left\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{y-1}{k-1} \right\rfloor.$$

If we now write $x = q_1(k - 1) + r_1$, $y = q_2(k - 1) + r_2$, with $1 \leq r_1, r_2 \leq k - 1$, the reduced inequality above fails to hold precisely when $r_1 + r_2 \geq k$. Given x , and hence r_1 , the choice $y = r_2 = k - r_1$ will thus ensure that (6) fails to hold provided $x + y \leq a - 1$. However, such a choice for y is not possible precisely when $x \geq q(k - 1) + 1 = a - r$, so that (6) always holds in only these cases. Finally, it is easy to verify that (6) holds if $x = a - 1$. This shows $\mathcal{S}^* = \{ a \lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \rfloor + dx : a - r \leq x \leq a - 1 \}$ if $2 \leq k \leq a - 1$.

If $k \geq a$, (6) reduces to $d((x+y) \bmod a) \leq d(x+y)$. Thus, $\mathcal{S}^* = \{ dx : 1 \leq x \leq a - 1 \}$, as claimed, since $r = a - 1$ and $\lfloor \frac{x-1}{k-1} \rfloor = 0$ in this case. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary: If a, d be relatively prime, positive integers, $k \geq 2$, and $a - 1 = q(k - 1) + r$, with $1 \leq r \leq k - 1$, then

$$g(a, d; k) = aq + d(a - 1),$$

$$g^*(a, d; k) = aq + d(a - r),$$

$$n^*(a, d; k) = r,$$

and

$$s^*(a, d; k) = aqr + \frac{1}{2}dr(2a - r - 1).$$

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank Professor R. Balasubramanian for introducing him to the problem, and Dr. C.S. Yogananda for arranging a copy of the eighth reference.

References

- [1] Bateman, P.T., Remark on a Recent Note on Linear Forms, *American Mathematical Monthly* **65** (1958), 517-518.
- [2] Brauer, A., On a Problem of Partitions, *American Journal of Mathematics* **64** (1942), 299-312.
- [3] Brauer, A. and Shockley, J.E., On a problem of Frobenius, *Crelle* **211** (1962), 215-220.
- [4] Brown, T.C. and Shiue, P.J., A remark related to the Frobenius problem, *Fibonacci Quarterly*, **31** (1993), 31-36.
- [5] Grant, D.D., On linear forms whose coefficients are in Arithmetic progression, *Israel Journal of Mathematics* **15** (1973), 204-209.
- [6] Hofmeister, G.R., Zu einem Problem von Frobenius, *Norske Videnskabers Selskabs Skrifter* **5** (1966), 1-37.
- [7] Nijenhuis, A. and Wilf, H.S., Representations of integers by linear forms in non negative integers, *Journal of Number Theory* **4** (1972), 98-106.
- [8] Patil, D.P. and Singh, Balwant, Generators for the derivation modules and the relation ideals of certain curves, *Manuscripta Mathematica* **68** (1990), 327-335.
- [9] Roberts, J.B., Note on Linear Forms, *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society* **7** (1956), 465-469.

- [10] Roberts, J.B., On a Diophantine problem, *Canadian Journal of Mathematics* **9** (1957), 219-222.
- [11] Rödseth, Ö.J., On a linear Diophantine problem of Frobenius, *Crelle* **301** (1978), 171-178.
- [12] Rödseth, Ö.J., On a linear Diophantine problem of Frobenius II, *Crelle* **307/308** (1979), 431-440.
- [13] Selmer, E.S., On the linear Diophantine problem of Frobenius, *Crelle* **293/294** (1977), 1-17.
- [14] Selmer, E.S. and Beyer, Ö., On the linear Diophantine problem of Frobenius in three variables, *Crelle* **301** (1978), 161-170.
- [15] Sylvester, J.J., Mathematical questions with their solutions, *The Educational Times* **41** (1884), 21.
- [16] Tripathi, A., The Coin Exchange Problem for Arithmetic Progressions, *American Mathematical Monthly* **101** (1994), no. 10, 779-781.